

A Critical Study of Kohlschütter's Method of Preparing Silver Hydrosol.

BY M. RAMAN NAYAR AND P. S. MACMAHON.

In an attempt to study the oxidizability of silver under various conditions we had occasion to prepare colloidal silver by reduction of silver oxide with hydrogen, a method described for the first time by Kohlschütter (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1908, 14, 49). Among other things he obtained sols of varying colours such as yellowish-brown, red, reddish-violet, blue, etc. He could not control their production nor could he produce them at will. He believed that the material of the reaction vessel affected the velocity of the reaction and also the colour of the sol. The difference in appearance was not to be attributed to the dissolved glass.

Kohlschütter's sol always contained a certain amount of electrolyte namely silver hydroxide which he said could be removed by further reduction with hydrogen in a blackened platinum dish without affecting the concentration of the colloid. The colloid particle also contained a certain proportion of oxide. "The proportion in which the oxide and silver stand in the real colloid is determined by the walls of the vessel in which the reduction is carried out ; it determines on the other hand the colour of the sol. The quantity of the combined oxide in the colloid is greater and fairly uniform in the yellowish-brown sols from soft glass and quartz vessels, it is smaller and very varying in the 'variegated' sols."

Pauli and Erlach (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 213) have repeated Kohlschütter's experiments and come to the conclusion that with pure silver oxide, pure hydrogen and conductivity water no sol is produced. A trace of alkali or sulphide (?) ions is necessary for the formation of the sol. In Kohlschütter's experiments the alkali must have been present in the silver oxide used, and the sulphide in the hydrogen from the Kipp.

Kohlschütter's assumption that the colloid particle is not affected by Pt-H treatment is questioned by Pauli, as also the alleged relation

between the material of the reaction vessel and the colour of the sol. Pauli proposes the constitution for the colloid particle to be either $(AgO, 5Ag_2O)$ or $[Ag(SH)_2, 4Ag_2O]$. The experimental basis for the formulæ is not clear from Pauli's paper.

Some of our experiments had been conducted before Pauli's paper appeared, but our observations did not tally with those of Pauli, even though the experimental conditions were similar and the reagents had gone through the same processes of purification (*Proc. Indian Science Congress, Lahore, 1927, p. 171*).

Since then we have discovered the cause of the discrepancy which we believe is of importance in the theory of the formation of silver sol.

In our experiments we took every reasonable precaution in preparing pure materials and shutting out impurities. Since Pauli's theory requires the presence of traces of electrolytes, *e.g.*, alkalis, which may be expected to be present in the silver oxide prepared chemically, it was desirable to have a perfect method of obtaining pure silver oxide. Such a method was found in the electrolysis of conductivity water with silver electrodes which yields a mixture of silver oxide and silver free from all impurities (*vide, Nayar and MacMahon, J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1930, 7, 589*).

The conductivity water employed by us had a value of K that ranged between 1.5 and 3×10^{-6} mhos. That the hydrogen was pure and contained no soluble impurities was shown by passing it into water for two hours or more and determining the conductivity of water before and after treatment with hydrogen.

Conductivity of water before treatment with hydrogen	=	2.240×10^{-6}	mhos.
„ „ after „ (2 hours)	=	$1.766 \times$	„

The conductivity had actually become less due to displacement of dissolved carbon dioxide by the hydrogen.

We used mainly silica vessels (flasks, beakers and tubes). For the repetition of Pauli's experiments Jena glass flasks were also used. All were thoroughly steamed before starting an experiment.

Repetition of Pauli's Experiments.—Pauli and Erlach after a series of experiments have come to the conclusion that with pure silver oxide, pure hydrogen and conductivity water no sol is formed. The purer the hydrogen the more difficult it is to obtain the sol. All

their experiments were devised with a view to improve the purity of hydrogen. The larger the number of washing bottles used for removing the impurities the longer the time taken for the formation of the sol. Thus with Kipp hydrogen and employing six washing bottles containing CuSO_4 , KMnO_4 , HgCl_2 , H_2SO_4 and Ag_2O respectively, the sol is not formed in 30 hours. Even under the worst conditions (commercial sulphuric acid, pure zinc in the Kipp, and only one washing bottle containing pure sulphuric acid) they obtained a thick sol in 8 hours. On the other hand employing electrolytic hydrogen and two spiral washing bottles with sulphuric acid the sol was not formed even after 72 hours.

We repeated the two sets of experiments but could not reproduce the above results. The Kipp contained pure sulphuric acid (Kahlbaum) diluted with distilled water, pure zinc and a few drops of pure copper sulphate solution to start the reaction. The washing bottles contained the same reagents mentioned above, belonging to Kahlbaum's analytical or pure grade excepting silver oxide which we prepared by the precipitation of silver nitrate with caustic soda, the former being used in slight excess. In this case the washing was done by decantation until brucine test failed to give any indication of nitrate, the final washing being done with conductivity water. The reaction vessel was a silica flask kept in a water-bath maintained approximately at 60° . The inlet tube for hydrogen was of silica. Air contamination was avoided by dipping the outlet tube from the reaction vessel in a beaker of distilled water. In 15 to 20 minutes from the commencement of the experiment a yellow colour was produced inside the flask. In one hour a wine-red sol, and in two hours a fairly thick sol was obtained. The experiment was conducted for five hours per day and the supernatant liquid, namely the sol, was decanted off and fresh conductivity water added each day. After 181 hours' reduction it was found that the oxide at the bottom of the vessel had been completely reduced and no more sol produced. The colour of the sol was generally wine-red by transmitted light and grey or greenish grey by reflected light. Occasionally a bluish or sometimes a pink sol was obtained, especially towards the close of the reduction. These sols were not so stable as the red ones, but coagulated in about four weeks. The above experiments were conducted with chemically prepared silver oxide. The following table refers to a repetition of the experiment with electrolytic oxide.

TABLE I

Duration (hrs.).	Colour and remarks.	Duration (hrs.).	Colour and remarks.
1	Orange-red.	6	Reddish, not deep.
3	Deep red.	5	Orange-red.
6	Deep red.	4	Yellowish-white, faintly pink by transmitted light.
7	Brownish-red.	7	Yellowish-white.
2	Orange-red.	4½	No sol.
3	Orange-red.	4	No sol; no more oxide left; residue pure silver.

The following tests were applied for the detection of oxide in the silver residues :

(1) The residus was shaken well with water and to the clear liquid hydrochloric acid was added. No opalescence, showing the absence of oxide.

(2) Residue was treated with a concentrated solution of KCl in a clean platinum or porcelain dish. A drop of phenolphthalein was added and the tint, if any, compared with a blank test. No red coloration was produced indicating the absence of oxide. This test was found to be exceedingly delicate for the detection of any trace of silver oxide.

Experiments with Silver-coated flasks.—Pauli carried out his experiments in silver flasks, and his conclusions were based upon results obtained from these, even though he said the same results were obtained with Jena glass flasks. Our experiments in silica and Jena glass flasks gave results contradictory to Pauli's experiments. The only part of Pauli's experiment which we could not repeat was the employment of silver flasks. In the course of our work, especially on continuous reduction of silver oxide without change of water, the reaction flask became coated with a beautiful mirror of silver. This approximated to Pauli's silver flask. Pauli also attempted some experiments in silvered flasks, but dismissed them as unsatisfactory.

In an experiment which had inadvertently been allowed to go on, it was found that a very thick greyish-white sol had been produced and the walls of the flask had a beautiful coating of silver mirror. When the liquid was replaced by fresh conductivity water no sol was produced, even though the residue at the bottom of the

flask gave tests for the presence of oxide. This put us on the right track for the explanation of the contradictory results, and some attempts were made to elucidate this phenomenon.

A Duro-glass flask was silvered inside by reduction of silver tartrate. On steaming it was found that scales of silver were coming off. To remove the alkali contamination, after the usual washing, the flask was filled with water and heated, at the same time a current of hydrogen was bubbled through for some hours. This flask was used for the next experiment.

TABLE II.

Silvered glass flask: Electrolytic silver oxide.

Duration. (hrs.).	Colour and remarks
6	White sol.
20	Thick yellowish-white sol.
	(Sol replaced by conductivity water.)
7	No sol produced.

The residue gave the phenolphthalein test for the presence of silver oxide. Similar results were obtained with chemically prepared silver oxide.

TABLE III.

Fresh silica flask: Chemically prepared silver oxide.

Duration (hrs.).	Colour and remarks.
8	Usual yellow colour in 15 minutes, red sol in 2 hours and thick milk-white sol in 8 hours.
18	Thin white sol and mirror.
	(Sol replaced by fresh water.)
10	Thick white sol.
	(Sol replaced by fresh water.)
16	White sol.
	(Sol replaced by fresh water.)
16	No sol.

The residue still contained oxide. The white sol was always unstable.

Silvered and Nonsilvered Silica flasks: Chemically prepared Silver Oxide.—That silvered surface has a negative catalytic effect is definitely proved by the following experiments:

(i) Silver oxide was reduced in a fresh silica flask continuously for 20 hours, when a mirror was formed and a thick yellowish-white sol was obtained. (This sol was kept aside when most of it settled down leaving a pale white supernatant liquid).

(ii) The sol was replaced by fresh conductivity water and reduction continued for another 4 hours. On examination a very faint white sol was found indicating that it was very unstable.

(iii) The residue was transferred to a fresh silica flask and reduction carried out for 3 hours only. The normal reddish sol was produced.

This conclusively shows that while silver oxide residue in a silvered flask produces a thin white unstable sol, in unsilvered flask the same residue produces the normal stable sol, proving thereby that the silver surface has a negative catalytic effect. (In the earlier experiments whenever the silver mirror was formed it was always removed by treatment with nitric acid followed by steaming.) That the material of the reaction vessel affected the velocity of reaction and the colour of the sol was also the opinion of Kohlschütter.

Further Observations on the Properties of the Sol.—In the course of our work we had occasion to prepare the sol under varying conditions which did not corroborate the following statement in Mellor's "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry," Vol. 3, pp. 555-6, evidently extracted from Kohlschütter's paper:—"Walls of soft glass or quartz give yellowish-brown hydrosols..... In 8 to 10 hours between half and one litre of intensely coloured sol is obtained. At temperatures below 50° the reduction is too slow; above 60° the sol is unstable."

We, on the other hand, usually obtained a wine-red sol (in transmitted light) in a quartz flask. The time required was only two to three hours. In less than an hour from the commencement of the experiment, the liquid becomes yellowish in colour and in two hours a deep red coloured sol is formed, especially if the experiment is started with fresh materials. The temperature of formation is not so well defined as stated above. The sol is formed even at 25°. The sixth washing bottle containing silver oxide employed for washing Kipp hydrogen (*vide supra*) was found to contain silver sol at the end of the experiment in one day, that is, in five hours. On the other

hand, the sol is certainly not unstable above 60°. When once formed, it could be boiled without coagulation, provided there was no solid matter at the bottom of the vessel. Further, the sol is formed readily at temperatures above 60°; our working temperature was usually 70-80°. The sol so produced was quite stable.

It was suggested that dialysis of such a sol (produced at the higher temperature) would result in coagulation. This had not been our experience either. We again prepared the sol at 80-85° (chemically prepared silver oxide, water of $K = 1.38 \times 10^{-6}$ mhos) in silica flask by reduction for 3 hours. The colour was red by transmitted light and greenish grey by reflected light. Dialysis was carried out in Pauli's folded dialyser (parchment paper) in a paraffined rectangular trough protected from atmospheric contamination by a paraffined glass cover. The course of dialysis was observed by conductivity determinations. The liquid outside the dialyser was changed every day.

Conductivity of sol on 1st day : $K_{10} = 23.66 \times 10^{-6}$ mhos.

.. 18th .. $K_{18} = 3.298$..

.. water outside dialyser : $K_{20} = 2.587$..

This sol was kept aside. Even after 18 months there was no coagulation. The concentration of the sol was found to be 0.0205 g. of Ag per litre. If the reduction of AgOH solution is carried on at the boiling point a coarse suspension results, which easily settles down to the bottom of the vessel.

Discussion.

Pauli in his first paper on Kohlschütter sol comes to the conclusion that a certain minimum amount of alkali ions is necessary before the silver sol can be produced, which he has incorporated in his "complex" theory of the mechanism of the sol formation. Silver oxide can dissociate in two ways :

The strong basic properties of the solution of silver oxide suggests that equation (2) predominates. But only (1) is capable of giving negative complex ions, even though according to the Law of Mass Action, the formation of appreciable quantities of these negative ions offers little probability. The trend of Pauli's argument is that the

presence of the large volumed alkali ion favours equation (1) by supplying the positive contra ions ("Gegenionen"), and in the absence of alkali ions no sol is to be expected. When once the sol is produced the alkali ions may be replaced by H⁺ ions by dialysis, which then gives rise to what Pauli calls an "azidoide." The dialysed silver sol is a very dilute acid or a "secondary azidoide."

The defect of this really complex theory is that Pauli's own experiments contradict it. Stable Bredig sol is produced in pure AgOH solution, containing no alkali ions (Pauli and Perlak, *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 39, 195). Our own observations are in contradiction to Pauli and Erlach's experiments on Kohlschütter sol. With silver oxide prepared chemically as well as electrolytically, pure hydrogen and conductivity water and thoroughly washed and steamed silica and Jenaglass vessels, we always obtained the Kohlschütter sol. The only time when we did not get the sol was when silvered vessels were used. The silver flasks used by Pauli must be presumed to have a negative catalytic effect. (Pauli however says that he obtained similar results—non-production of sol in Jena-glass vessels also, especially after long use).

Instead of this round-about method of explanation, the dissociation of silver oxide may be pictured as:

where the Ag⁺ ions may be displaced by H⁺ ions in the process of reduction by hydrogen (*cf.* electromotive series of elements), and the negative ion (AgO)', becomes the condensation centre for the formation of the colloid particle. The presence of alkali may favour this, but it is not essential. That silver oxide can behave as an amphoteric oxide has been shown by the work of Eric Laue (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 165, 325). The presence of a stronger alkali may suppress or reverse the ionization (2) and hence favour equation (1). Thus the alkali may be expected to facilitate the formation of the sol. The centre of importance then would be shifted from the alkali ion to the hydroxyl ion.

The catalytic effect (negative in this case) of the silver surface may perhaps be attributed to the electromotive behaviour of the metal. It is well known that a silver electrode is electrically posi-

tive with respect to a solution containing silver ions. A silver surface then has the same effect as an increase in the concentration of Ag⁺ ions near the walls of the vessel, where apparently the reaction is taking place. This would result in the reversal of equation (1) and hence the absence of the necessary condensation centre for the formation of the colloid particles.

A silica or glass surface cannot be expected to behave similarly to silver. At the worst the former can only be indifferent to the chemical reaction taking place in its neighbourhood; but probably it helps the reaction catalytically, *i.e.*, behaves as a positive catalyst. Pauli's experimental observation that Jena glass vessels behave similarly to silver requires confirmation. Our experiments contradict it.

Summary.

(1) For the formation of Kohlschütter sol the presence of alkali is not essential as stated by Pauli. The walls of the experimenting vessel determine the nature of the sol. Silvered vessels produce no sol or only thin pale white unstable sols. Silica or glass vessels invariably give rise to wine-red stable sols.

(2) The contradiction between Pauli's experimental results and ours on Kohlschütter sol has been traced to the negative catalytic effect of silver, of which material the former's experimenting vessels were made.

(3) Stable Kohlschütter sol has been prepared at 85°. Reduction of silver oxide solution near the boiling point produces a coarse suspension.

